

MESOSCALE CLIMATE MODELING ABOVE A METHANE LAKE ON TITAN

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Starting point: the mtWRF model

Research Paper

Air-sea interactions on titan: Lake evaporation, atmospheric circulation, and cloud formation

Scot C.R. Rafkin^{*}, Alejandro Soto

Icarus 2020

Implementation of a radiation scheme

Schneider et al 2012 (gray scheme)
Tomasko et al 2008 (Huygens/DISR)

The general solution does not change

Initial methane plume
(a few hours)

Beginning of the sea breeze
(~12h)

Extended sea breeze
(> 1 day)

contours = CH_4 mixing ratio (every 1 g/kg)
lake of 300 km at the center

NEW

Diurnal evolution of the sea breeze

+

stronger winds over land at night

Night [1-3 am]

NEW

Diurnal evolution of the sea breeze

+

stronger winds over land at night

Night [1-3 am]

Day [1-3 pm]

NEW Less cooling of the lake

with radiation ☀️

without radiation

⇒ lake hotter (up to +1.5 K) + undergo diurnal variations (+/- 0.3 K)

NEW A different energy balance

with radiation ☀️

without radiation

Fluxes to the surface (at the shore)

Fluxes to the surface (at the shore)

At equilibrium:

$$\text{latent heat} \approx \text{sensible heat} + \text{solar} + \text{IR}$$

Summary: radiative transfer matters, we can't ignore it!

- Diurnal variations of the sea breeze:
 - extends over land at night
 - limited by strong convection cells during the day
- Change in the energy balance: we should not neglect solar and IR fluxes
 - more CH₄ evaporation
 - diurnal cooling/heating of the lake
- Affected by initial humidity and seasons

Perspective: application to moist surfaces all over Titan
(in particular at the Dragonfly landing site at the equator)